

THE POWER OF UML IN COMMUNICATION: BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN DEVELOPERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

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Abstract. *The collaborative nature of software development necessitates seamless communication between developers and stakeholders, a group that often comprises individuals with diverse technical backgrounds. This disparity in technical expertise can lead to misunderstandings, mismatched expectations, and ultimately, roadblocks in project progress. Imagine a scenario where meticulous coding efforts culminate in a complex feature that fails to align with stakeholder expectations. This communication gap, frequently caused by technical processes and a lack of shared understanding, can be quite expensive, resulting in delays, rework, and potential project failure. UML diagrams emerge as a powerful tool to bridge this communication gap. They act as a visual language that transcends technical complexities, enabling all parties involved to grasp the software system's functionalities, structure, and behavior in a clear and concise manner. By leveraging a standardized set of symbols and notations, UML diagrams present a visual representation of the system, fostering a common ground for developers and stakeholders to collaborate effectively. This article explores how Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagrams can bridge this communication gap by providing a visual representation of the software system's design and functionalities. We discuss how different UML diagrams, such as use case diagrams and class diagrams, can be used to visualize user interactions, system structure, and data flow. We will explore how these diagrams can be employed during the design phase to foster discussions and collaboration between developers and stakeholders, ensuring a shared understanding of the project goals and functionalities.*

Keywords: *UML diagrams, communication, software development, stakeholders, developers, visual language.*

Introduction

Software development is essential in our modern world because it underpins nearly everything we do with technology. The success of any software development project hinges on effective communication between developers and stakeholders. These stakeholders can encompass a wide range of individuals, from business analysts and project managers to clients and end-users. While they share a common goal of delivering a functional and successful software system, the technical expertise across these groups can vary significantly. This disparity in technical fluency can breed misunderstandings, mismatched expectations, and ultimately, roadblocks that stall project progress and inflate costs [1], [2], [3].

Imagine a situation where a development team diligently encodes a complex function based on their technical understanding, only to later discover that it does not match the vision of the stakeholders. This communication gap, often rooted in technical jargon and a lack of shared understanding of the system's functionalities, can be highly detrimental. It can lead to costly delays, rework of features that need to be redesigned, and in extreme cases, project failure [4], [5].

UML diagrams emerge as a powerful tool to bridge this communication gap and foster a collaborative environment. They act as a visual language that transcends technical complexities. By leveraging a standardized set of symbols and notations, UML diagrams provide a visual representation of the software system's design, functionalities, and behavior [6]. This visual representation creates a common ground for developers and stakeholders to engage in meaningful discussions. Developers can explain functionalities using the diagrams, pointing to specific elements and interactions. Stakeholders can ask questions, provide feedback from their perspective, and ensure the system aligns with their needs. This iterative process fosters a shared understanding of the project goals and desired outcomes, ultimately leading to a more successful software development lifecycle. Additionally, UML diagrams are used by software professionals to reflect different aspects of software system architecture [7].

The Role Of Uml Diagrams

Most often, a UML diagram is used to analyze existing software, model new software, plan software development, and prioritize. Simply put, if you need a way to visualize and plan the software development process, the UML diagram is incredibly useful. For example Visual Representation. This is a complex technical concepts which can be difficult to understand through text descriptions alone [8]. UML diagrams offer a visual representation of the system, making it easier for non-technical stakeholders to comprehend the overall design and functionalities [9]. Moreover, Shared Understanding - by presenting the system design visually, UML diagrams establish a common ground for discussion and collaboration. Developers can explain functionalities using the diagrams, while stakeholders can provide feedback from their perspective. This fosters a shared understanding of the project goals and desired outcomes. In addition, Early Feedback and Course Correction. UML diagrams are created during the design phase, allowing stakeholders to provide early feedback on the proposed functionalities and user interactions. This early input helps identify potential issues before significant coding begins, saving time and resources in the long run. prevent software errors, a comprehensive set of 19 modern consistency rules has been developed to guarantee the coherence of UML diagrams. These rules are designed to benefit developers, educators, and researchers, promoting flexible software development and enhancing productivity[10].

UML Diagram Types

UML diagrams are usually divided into two separate groups: structural diagrams and behavioral diagrams or interaction diagrams. UML structural diagrams illustrate the organization of a system by representing its components such as classes, objects, and packages. They represent the elements that make up the system and the relationships between them. Behavior diagrams illustrate the behavior of a system, they are used extensively to describe the functionality of software systems. One of the main factors in the widespread usage of UML is the availability of UML tools. There are many different types of UML tools, ranging from free open-source software to expensive ones. Beyond only creating diagrams, these tools are quite versatile. They can use design patterns, mine requirements, build code from the design, reverse-engineer existing code, and conduct impact and complexity analyses. These benefits, together with the profusion of UML tools themselves, have made UML the standard modeling and programming language in the software engineering industry.

Class diagrams demonstrate the main elements of the system – classes and their interrelationships. Although the technical details may be less clear to stakeholders without a

technical background, they can still understand the overall structure by seeing the main components and how they interact. Besides that, we can use a new method and tool to automatically create a class diagram with the help of Java program. The tool analyzes the program, identifies its components, and then builds a class diagram representation in a table format. This can save developers time and effort compared to manually creating class diagrams [11]. We can automatically determine the quality of software systems at the initial design stages in the production of a software product: various restrictions, requests [12]. In a word,

Class diagrams are a fundamental part of object-oriented design, providing a blueprint for the system's structure. They help in understanding the relationships and hierarchies within the system, serving as a critical reference throughout the development process. By defining classes, attributes, methods, and their interactions, class diagrams facilitate communication among stakeholders and provide a clear vision of the system architecture.

Fig-1. Class diagrams for Online shopping project”

Sequence Diagrams depict the sequence of messages exchanged between objects in a specific scenario. They illustrate how objects interact with each other to complete a task, which can be helpful for stakeholders to understand the system's behavior under various conditions. For example, the use of sequence diagrams is important when measuring the size and complexity of software functions [13]. The role of sequence diagrams is also great in organizing a simplified workflow for managing book credit requests in the library management system. This drawing presents the main interactions between members, librarians and the system to ensure an effective credit process.

In addition, activity diagrams are a valuable tool for modeling the dynamic aspects of a system, including its workflows and business processes. In a library management system they can be used to: visualize the workflow, identify bottlenecks and inefficiencies, communicate processes, document requirements, support system development.

A Component Diagram is a type of UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram that provides a high-level view of a system's architecture by illustrating its components and their relationships.

Component diagrams are a crucial tool in software engineering, providing a clear and structured way to visualize the components of a system and their relationships. This visualization

not only aids in the design and development processes but also enhances communication among stakeholders. Understanding the multifaceted role of component diagrams can significantly improve project outcomes and collaboration. Component diagrams are essential for understanding System Architecture, Promoting Modularity, Facilitating Communication, Supporting Dependency Management, Enhancing Documentation, Guiding Impact Analysis, Encouraging Reusability.

Fig-2. Sequence diagram for “Library management system”

Fig-3. Component diagrams for Online visiting card project”

Object diagrams are a type of structural diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) that represent the instances of classes at a particular moment in time. They provide a snapshot of the system's state, illustrating how objects interact and relate to each other.

UML As A Communication Tool

The success of any software development project hinges on clear and concise communication between various stakeholders. Developers, designers, analysts, and even non-technical clients all need to grasp the system's intricacies to ensure a smooth and efficient development process. This is where Unified Modeling Language (UML) shines. Beyond its core function of modeling object-oriented systems, UML diagrams emerge as powerful communication tools, fostering collaboration and a shared understanding throughout the development lifecycle.

Collaborative Creation: Involve stakeholders in the process of creating UML diagrams. This fosters a sense of ownership and improves their understanding of the system design.

Tailored Explanations: When presenting UML diagrams to stakeholders, tailor the level of detail and technical explanations to their background and expertise.

Iterative Refinement: UML diagrams are not static documents. Refine and update them throughout the development process to reflect changes in the system design and ensure stakeholders remain informed.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, diagrams in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) play a key role in bridging the communication gap between developers and stakeholders in software development projects. The complexity of modern software systems requires clear and effective communication between all parties involved, and UML provides a standardized visual language that facilitates this understanding. Using various types of UML diagrams such as class diagrams, sequence diagrams, and use case diagrams, teams can visually represent the architecture, functionality, and behavior of a system, making it easier for both technical and non-technical stakeholders to understand complex concepts.

One of the main advantages of using UML diagrams is to improve mutual understanding between team members and stakeholders. When everyone has access to a visual representation of the system, it facilitates collaboration and coordination of project goals. This clarity helps to identify potential differences in understanding at an early stage of the development process, allowing timely discussion and correction of errors. Early detection of errors can significantly reduce the costs and efforts associated with refinement, which ultimately leads to increased efficiency of the development lifecycle.

Moreover, UML diagrams serve as valuable documentation throughout the software development lifecycle. They contain important information about the design and structure of the system, which can be referenced during development, testing and deployment. This documentation is especially useful for further maintenance and updates. As software systems evolve, UML diagrams can be adapted to reflect changes in requirements or architecture, ensuring that all stakeholders are informed about the current state of the system. Such adaptability is vital in an environment where project specifications change frequently, allowing development teams to respond quickly and effectively.

In addition, UML diagrams help to create a collaborative environment in which developers, project managers, business analysts and clients can work more efficiently. By providing a common visual language, UML reduces the likelihood of misunderstandings. This spirit of collaboration not only improves team dynamics, but also leads to more successful implementation of software systems that meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders.

In this way, by using UML diagrams, development teams can develop a culture of collaboration and transparency. The visual nature of UML diagrams allows teams to articulate complex ideas clearly, leading to more effective decision-making and more successful software development results. As the software market continues to develop, the importance of effective communication and documentation using UML will only grow, making it an indispensable tool in the software development process.

REFERENCES

1. Chaudron, Michel R V, Heijstek, Werner, Nugroho, Ariadi(2012). How effective is UML modeling ?. *Software & System modeling*. 11, 571-580. DOI 10.1007/s10270-012-0278-4

2. Goto, Takaaki and Goto, Takaaki and Nishino, Tetsuro and Yaku, Takeo and Tsuchida, Kensei(2014). Generation of UML package diagrams based on an attribute graph grammar. *Journal of Computer Science*, 5(4), 606-615. doi:10.1016/j.jocs.2014.02.005
3. Vanwormhoudt, Gilles and Caron, Olivier and Caron, Olivier. Aspectual templates in UML. *Software & Systems Modeling*.(2017) 16(2), 469-497. DOI 10.1007/s10270-015-0463-3
4. Störrle, Harald(2018). On the impact of size to the understanding of UML diagrams. *Software & Systems Modeling*. 17(1), 115-134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10270-016-0529-x>
5. Kchaou, Dhikra and Bouassida, Nadia and Ben-Abdallah, Hanene(2016). Managing the Impact of UML Design Changes on Their Consistency and Quality. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*. 41(8), 2863-2881. DOI 10.1007/s13369-016-2040-7
6. Moral, Cristian and de Antonio, Angélica and Ferre, Xavier and Ramirez, Jaime(2021). A proposed UML-based common model for information visualization systems. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. 80(8), 12541-12579. doi:10.1007/s11042-020-10306-9
7. Ozkaya, Mert, Erata, Ferhat(2020). A survey on the practical use of UML for different software architecture viewpoints. *Information and Software Technology*. 121, 106275. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2020.106275
8. Störrle, Harald(2018). On the impact of size to the understanding of UML diagrams. *Software & Systems Modeling*. 17(1), 115-134. DOI 10.1007/s10270-016-0529-x
9. Cvetković, Jovana, Cvetković, Milan(2019). Evaluation of UML diagrams for test cases generation:Case study on depression of internet addiction. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*. 525, 1351-1359. doi:10.1016/j.physa.2019.03.101
10. Kulkarni, RN, Pani Rama Prasad, rediffmailco P, Professor, Asst(2021). Abstraction of UML Class Diagram from the Input Java Program. *Int. J. Advanced Networking and Applications*. 4644-4649.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/ce23c99ba79a89ace91fe7f82546da46/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=886380>
11. Farré, Carles, Queralt, Anna, Rull, Guillem, Teniente, Ernest, Urpí, Toni(2013). Automated reasoning on UML conceptual schemas with derived information and queries. *Information and Software Technology*. 55(9), 1529-1550. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2013.02.010
12. Sellami, Asma, Hakim, Hela, Abran, Alain, Ben-Abdallah, Hanène(2015). A measurement method for sizing the structure of UML sequence diagrams. *Information and Software Technology*. 59, 222-232. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2014.11.002
13. Sellami, Asma, Hakim, Hela, Abran, Alain, Ben-Abdallah, Hanène(2015). A measurement method for sizing the structure of UML sequence diagrams. *Information and Software Technology*. 59, 222-232. doi:10.1016/j.infsof.2014.11.002